

1 **New trend on chemical structure representation learning in toxicology: In reviews of machine**
2 **learning model methodology**

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 Computer-assisted virtual screening using structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models is a surrogate
18 method for reducing the need for costly animal experiments. However, traditional QSAR models face
19 significant challenges, such as the 'activity cliff' phenomenon and small datasets, which limit their ability to
20 generalize and predict toxicity. This review examines transistion of digital encodings form in molecules and
21 its corresponding models, introducing from molecule descriptors to three advanced types of molecular
22 representations based on deep learning techniques. We highlight the importance of deep learning models

23 that can not only capture molecular similarity in chemical space to address the 'activity cliff' problem but
 24 also improve model performance through feature fusion. As alternative solutions to reduce reliance on
 25 feature engineering potentially, graph neural network, convolutional neural network and large language
 26 model and their related training paradigm such as transfer learning could give another opportunity for
 27 toxicity model setting in terms of data insufficient dealing etc. This work could help potential deep learning
 28 modelers to build robust model, setting the stage for groundbreaking advancements in further development
 29 and application of toxicity prediction models.

30

31 **Key words:** Risk management, Deep representative learning, chemical structure, toxicity prediction,
 32 QSAR

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72 **Main Text**

73 **1. Introduction**

74 Prediction of chemical toxicity and physical properties is one of the most important applications of machine
75 learning method recently(Van Noorden, 2018). This suite of models aims to reduce societal costs and time by
76 substituting expensive experiments with cost-effective computational methods(Zhao et al., 2022). It has
77 been widely applied from toxicology to environmental health in the past few decades(Banerjee et al., 2018).
78 This research field is usually called quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) in chemistry, which
79 is a method to construct molecular fingerprints (FPs) or molecular descriptors (MD) from molecular
80 structures and establish linear and nonlinear relationships between molecular properties(Fujita & Winkler,
81 2016). By applying this QSAR mathematical expression, new substances can be estimated rapidly for their
82 molecular characteristics without wet experiments conducting, which is used for chemical substance
83 screening or designing new compounds with specific properties(Ban et al., 2017; Capuzzi et al., 2018). The
84 pioneering work can be traced back to 1962 with the publication by Hansch (Hansch et al., 1962), which
85 introduced the concept of QSAR. Since then, QSAR has been widely applied in scientific research. As
86 machine learning advances in 1990's, algorithms in the field of artificial intelligence in chemistry have also
87 been widely incorporated into the term QSAR(Muratov et al., 2020).

88

89 Classical models used expert-compiled features to represent molecules, taking linear regression as an
90 example, most of the QSAR tasks in the past were based on FPs or MD such as Morgan(Rogers & Hahn,
91 2010), molecular access system (MACCS)(Durant et al., 2002), Topological torsion, or based on
92 octanol-water coefficients logP, pKa as features X, and fitted the weights w and b of the X features to get
93 the mathematical formula between the feature vector and the Y value, which is the molecular property to be

94 predicted. This modeling principle is widely applied in the research of molecular property prediction
95 models and is also utilized in the prediction of molecular toxicity. The development of artificial intelligence
96 algorithms in 2000's such as Random Forests (RF)(Breiman, 2001), Support Vector Machine (SVM),
97 EXtreme Gradint Boosting (Xgboost), Deep Neural Networks (DNN) and other supervised learning
98 algorithms has greatly expanded the ability of QSAR algorithms to fit nonlinear data(J.-J. Zhu et al., 2023).
99 Research combining molecular descriptors or molecular fingerprints with machine learning achieved
100 numerous outstanding results from 1990 to 2010. However, with the onset of the big data era, the number
101 of molecular descriptors has gradually increased. The selection of these descriptors tests the modeler's
102 understanding of the problem and becomes crucial to the success of the model's predictions (Mauri et al.,
103 2006). When modelers lack sufficient prior knowledge about the problem to be modeled, they often face
104 the challenge of evaluating thousands of descriptors to get the best one for the prediction target, which is
105 time-consuming and increases the workload. In even worse scenarios, existing descriptors may not
106 adequately fit the problem, meaning that modelers might need to design molecular descriptors specifically
107 for the issue at hand. Although deepTox achieved commendable results in the Tox21 challenge (Mayr et al.,
108 2016), however, these methods are still inherently heavily dependent on the pre-processing step of data -
109 feature engineering.

110

111 To alleviate this situation, since the 2010s, driven by the development of deep learning, the development
112 patterns in the molecular property prediction and generation fields have changed. Deep representation
113 learning, however, rather than manually selecting expert-derived features for building predictive models, it
114 involves training models to automatically learn meaningful features from data. The emergence of these
115 technologies heralds the birth of more intelligent learning techniques, leading to the development of a

116 series of end-to-end learning technologies. By intergrating it, a more promising training paradigm is
117 gradually being promoted, which is to use deep representation learning to develop embeddings of data for
118 pre-trained big data tasks and then fine-tune them for downstream small relative tasks (Devlin et al., 2019
119 conference of the north american chapter of the association for computational linguistics: Human language
120 technologies (naacl hlt 2019), vol. 1/2019). This emerging paradigm has been applied to the fields of
121 computer vision and natural language process and made remarkable achievements. High-quality
122 representations should retain as much data information as possible, it should be low-dimensional, compact,
123 and able to distinguish different molecules. They should also capture the hidden information and the
124 common principles that apply to many tasks. These representations, together with the power of deep neural
125 networks to uncover complex nonlinearity, not only simplified the data preprocessing steps, but also have
126 achieved the best performance(Kearnes et al., 2016).

127
128 In this work, we focus on emerging trend in chemical molecule processing techniques from “feature
129 engineering” to “deep representation learning” as well as their related training paradigm such as
130 self-supervised learning and transfer learning. In the next section, we begin with an overview of the feature
131 engineering of prediction of molecule toxicity in environmental science with a discussion of their
132 (dis)advantages. Following that, by reviewing the short history of deep learning technique in molecule
133 science, we will discuss deep representation learning-enabled molecular feature extraction as a promising
134 alternative methodology to relieve the dependence on hand-crafted feature with potential applications in
135 evaluation of toxicity chemical. Additionally, we will introduce some public datasets and interpretable
136 algorithms to fairly evaluate the performance of newly developed deep learning models and to demystify
137 the black-box nature of these high-performance models. We propose that these new series of training

138 paradigms will help to establish more robust data-driven model and boost their performance of prediction
139 and generalization even when encountering small datasets in the field of environmental safety.

140

141 **2. Overview of descriptors-based molecule toxicity prediction technique**

142 **2.1 Bespoke representations for toxicity QSAR modeling**

143 Since the 1960s, molecular descriptors are numerical representations or features that describe the physical
144 properties (such as dipole moment, charge) or molecular structure (number of carbon atoms, number of
145 rings, molecular weight) of molecules, used in mathematical modeling. While molecular fingerprints (e.g.
146 MACCS, ECFPs) are another class of features that directly encode the molecular structure. Molecular
147 fingerprints can be classified into substructure fingerprints and topological fingerprints. The former
148 encodings approach are determined by whether specific predefined substructures (functional groups) are
149 present or absent in the molecule, and they are represented using binary vectors (e.g. Either one or zero).
150 The latter are based on the topological structure of the entire molecular graph. ECFPs, for example, also
151 known as “Morgan fingerprint”, are a common example of this type. It encodes each atom in a molecule by
152 a set of attributes such as connectivity number, atomic number, charge number, etc. These attributes are
153 then mapped to a 32-bit integer value to initialize the ECFP algorithm. In each iteration, the encoding of
154 each atom is updated by incorporating the encoding of its neighboring atoms, and the radius of the
155 neighborhood is increased. This process is repeated until a desired radius is reached, and then the final
156 encoding of each atom is concatenated into a vector and hashed into the final molecular fingerprint(Wigh et
157 al., 2022).

158

159 Over time, researchers introduced more advanced descriptors and fingerprints(Kier & Hall, 1990; Voelkel,

1994), which could capture fields surrounding molecules aiming at molecular interaction researching(Roy et al., 2009). The success of these representations is grounded in the principle of “molecular similarity”, stating that similar molecules should make similar properties/interactions(Hendrickson, 1991). This would allow retrieval of potentially active substances on the basis of known active substances and further excavate their active substructure. These descriptors have been adopted in AI/Machine learning competitions such as on MoleculeNet benchmark datasets to offer state-of-the-art (SOTA) performance in many applications. Additionally, they can be easily calculated and compared freely in specialized software packages such as RDKit(Cao et al., 2013; J. Dong et al., 2018) in Python and R programming languages, which could currently calculate 208 descriptors and 5 fingerprints. Whereas some online webservice and database such as PubChem, ChEMBL, E-Dragon, ChemDes(J. Dong et al., 2015) could also provided precomputed descriptors for user that does not require programming knowledge friendly.

171

172 **2.2 Classical machine learning method**

173 With the advent of artificial intelligence techniques, classical machine learning (ML) methods, such as RF, 174 SVM, Naive Bayes (NB), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), gradient boosting decision trees (GBDT) and 175 Xgboost, are increasingly used for predicting molecular toxicity in the environmental domain. They are 176 described in detail in Table 1. During data preprocessing, modelers prefer using molecular fingerprints and 177 descriptors to characterize chemical substances. This is because they offer good predictive accuracy while 178 maintaining interpretability. For instance, Yang(Yang & Zhang, 2013) involved log P , pKa and two 179 electronic descriptors into QSAR model to predict toxicity of new aromatic halogenated DBPs. Sun 180 modeled the rat acute oral toxicity of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons with eight 2D descriptors via 181 multiple linear regression(G. Sun et al., 2021). Ai calculated 12 molecular fingerprints for 400 chemicals.

182 These fingerprints were used as inputs for an ensemble-SVM classification model to predict aquatic
183 toxicity(Ai et al., 2019). Table 2 summarizes some recent studies using classical machine learning with
184 descriptors-based representation to predict the toxic properties of environmental compounds and achieved
185 good results(Ciallella et al., 2021; Hao et al., 2023; L. He et al., 2019; Kurosaki et al., 2020; Kwon et al.,
186 2023; Peets et al., 2022; Raza et al., 2019; Samanipour et al., 2022; Shen et al., 2021; X. Sun et al., 2020;
187 Zhao et al., 2022; K. Zhu et al., 2021). Jeong summarized in the context of toxicity prediction that MD
188 were used in 57 articles, while MF were used in 56 articles(Jeong & Choi, 2022).

189

190 **2.3 Limitations for descriptors-based featurization technique**

191 While MD and FP-based algorithms perform many forecasting tasks effectively, which relies on the
192 principle of chemical similarity discussed earlier, they still suffer from some limitations for QSAR
193 modeling(Hendrickson, 1991). The occurrence of activity cliffs (Muratov et al., 2020) is a major reason that
194 limits QSAR prediction, that is, small changes in the structure of compounds will lead to significant
195 changes in molecular activity. For example, Matched molecular pairs (MMP) (Griffen et al., 2011) shows
196 that structurally similar molecules can have very different activities, and vice versa. Therefore, the MD and
197 FPs would face the problem of predicting different outcomes for very similar molecules. As a result, a more
198 expressive and succinct way of capturing molecular similarity is needed. Additionally, the counting-based
199 fingerprint representation method produces discrete and non-unique representations, which lose some
200 information due to bit collisions(Haghighatlari et al., 2020). For instance, in extended-connectivity
201 fingerprints (ECFPs), each molecule is encoded with a unique integer identifier, and there is no similarity
202 concept between fragments. The difference between chloroethyl and fluoromethyl is like its difference from
203 benzene. FCFPs (functional-class fingerprints) , an improved method of ECFPs, uses generic atom types to

204 force similar groups to encode the same, which will inevitably reduce the expressiveness of fingerprints by
205 mapping similar but not identical fragments to the same bit(Rogers & Hahn, 2010).

206

207 To address the limitations of current descriptors, common approaches include adding more
208 physicochemical details to the eigenmatrix or designing new descriptors that better correlate with target
209 attributes (Grisoni et al., 2018). Designing good descriptors for new and unexplored systems is especially
210 challenging, since our understanding of the causal mechanisms and data distributions underlying the
211 observed outcomes is limited (Haghighatlari et al., 2020). Furthermore, different descriptors capture
212 different aspects of information, and no single representation excels at all tasks. For instance, numerical
213 descriptors such as molecular weight or polarity can well predict molecular properties related to variables
214 such as boiling point, but they struggle in complex molecular docking tasks that require structural
215 information of the molecules. The choice of representation largely depends on its specific application, so it
216 is best to stack the features as much as possible to enrich the representations to enhance their correlation
217 with the target attributes(Grisoni et al., 2018). Consequently, researchers have to take much effort to assess
218 or combine multiple descriptors to achieve good predictive performance.

219

220 **3. Overview of deep representation learning-based molecular feature automation extraction** 221 **technique**

222 The application of machine learning methods in molecular toxicity prediction in environmental science is
223 experiencing explosive growth. A new promising feature approach, known as representation learning
224 through deep learning models, has been adopted to solve the aforementioned limitations and enhance the
225 model performance(Tan et al., 2023). The deep learning paradigm directly learns compact and expressive

226 representations from the observed data without descriptors comparison, in which the learned embeddings
227 can be lossless and automatically extract any information present in the molecule. Hence, these learned
228 embeddings may be more effective in predicting necessary properties for downstream tasks compared to
229 conventional descriptors or fingerprints. This paradigm shift is the driving force behind the deep learning
230 resurgence in computer vision and natural language processing domains(Bengio et al., 2013; Krizhevsky et
231 al., 2017a; Vaswani et al., Advances in neural information processing systems 30 (nips 2017)/2017), where
232 deep neural networks now achieve remarkable performance in object recognition and sentiment
233 analysis(Devlin et al., 2019 conference of the north american chapter of the association for computational
234 linguistics: Human language technologies (naacl hlt 2019), vol. 1/2019). Compared to feature-based
235 representation (Fig. 2), these deep neural networks can automatically learn unique and continuous
236 representations, and can learn molecular similarity concepts that are specific to the task. These methods
237 will be explained in detail in the following section.

238

239 **3.1 Learning on molecular graphs**

240 **Graph encodings**

241 A graph is one of the most intuitive ways to represent molecular structures. Any molecule can be treated as
242 a mathematical graph, where dots are atoms and bonds are edges. In many deep learning applications,
243 molecular graphs can be characterized by a set of vertex and edge features.

244 **Graph-based modelling**

245 Graph neural network (GNNs) do not rely on predefined representation but instead learn them from the
246 data using convolutional kernels, which aggregate information from a node's neighbors (Fig.3). These
247 kernels allow GNNs to create a feature representation for each atom or particle, based on their chemical

248 properties (e.g., nuclear charge or type) and their chemical environment (Coley et al., 2017; Gilmer et al.,
249 2017). The feature representation is updated at each neural network layer by applying the convolutional
250 kernels with weights are learned during the training process (Kipf & Welling, 2016). The final layer of the
251 GNN produces a feature representation that encodes the many-body information required to predict the
252 target property. This representation is typically dense and continuous, and although it may not be easily
253 interpretable by humans, it has been shown to be very flexible and capable of capturing complex
254 relationships given enough data. Furthermore, GNNs(Shishir et al., 2021) have been demonstrated to
255 predict molecular properties more accurately than human-engineered molecular descriptors on several
256 biologically relevant properties(Liu et al., 2019; K. Yang et al., 2019). Duvenaud(Duvenaudt et al.,
257 Advances in neural information processing systems 28 (nips 2015)/2015) used graph neural networks to
258 provide a generalization of the ECFP algorithm, which learns continuous representations of molecular
259 fragments by replacing the hash function with a neural network layer. This method enables similar
260 encoding of molecular fragments based on the prediction task and enhances the expressiveness of the
261 representations by learning continuous similarity measures that can capture subtle molecular differences.
262 Moreover, the network parameters are directly learned from the training data, which implies that the
263 molecular similarity concept is defined by the objective function. Cheng (Cheng & Ng, 2019) presented
264 that GCN and multitask neural network could have average 0.916 AUC score on PFASs' bioactivity
265 prediction. More relevant works could be found in Table 3 (Anand et al., 2024; X. Liu et al., 2023; H. Wang
266 et al., 2022; Zang et al., 2023).

267

268 **3.2 Learning on image representation**

269 **Image array**

270 Our common images in life are grayscale and color images. A grayscale image is represented as a 2D
271 (width and height) array, where each element corresponds to a pixel value, whereas a color image is
272 represented as a 3D array, where the last dimension has size 3 (for red, green, and blue channels). Each
273 pixel in an RGB image has three values (one for each channel), representing the intensity of red, green, and
274 blue at that location. You can feed these images into a Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for tasks
275 like classification, object detection, or segmentation.

276

277 **Computer vision model**

278 Convolutional neural networks (CNN), among the earliest deep learning models in computer visions (CV)
279 for processing images(Krizhevsky et al., 2017b), are similarly employed for small molecule representation
280 learning recently(Van Tran et al., 2023). 1D CNNs accept sequences of data, such as time-series data or 1D
281 signals. The input data is typically a 2D array, where one dimension represents the sequence length and the
282 other dimension represents the features. 2D CNNs work with images or other 2D data, where the first two
283 dimensions represent the image height and width, and the third dimension represents the channels. 2D
284 CNNs process images and slide the kernel in two directions and they are widely used for computer vision
285 tasks (Fig.4).

286

287 In these models, convolution is used to extract and transform features from local pixels (known as filters),
288 resulting in a weighted representation that aggregates local patterns(Chuang et al., 2020). This approach
289 allows the model to efficiently discern and isolate advanced features from any segment of the input(Bengio

290 et al., 2013). Convolutional embeddings have been widely applied to various molecular representations,
291 such as voxel grids that depict the electron density of a specific molecular conformation in
292 three-dimensional space. However, CNN-based embeddings also have limitations, such as the lack of
293 rotational invariance mentioned above(Gens & Domingos, 2014). If a molecule is rotated, the embeddings
294 produced by the given input image or 3D electron density grid may change, potentially leading to different
295 predictions for the same molecule. This drawback limits the favorability of CNNs for learning molecular
296 representations. For example, Wang(Wang et al., 2021) represented molecular structures using 3D surface
297 electrostatic potential point clouds, and designed SepPCNET model with conv1D as the core feature
298 extraction layer to perform molecular toxicity detection on 1317 chemicals, achieving an accuracy of
299 88.3%. More examples are presented in Table 3 (C. Chen et al., 2024; Daghighi et al., 2024; G. Dong et al.,
300 2023; P. Sun & Zhao, 2024; Q. Yuan et al., 2019).

301

302 **3.3 Learning on string representation**

303 **String encodings**

304 Early chemical information systems mainly focused on the storage and retrieval of small molecule
305 information, so they needed to seek compact and unique molecular representations to improve storage
306 efficiency and fast indexing. The most commonly used is Simplified molecular-input line-entry
307 system(Weininger, 1988) (SMILES), which uses a string of ASCII characters to represent organic
308 molecules, where letters are used to represent atoms, symbols and numbers to encode the types of bonds.
309 However, SMILES cannot handle non-central chirality or tautomeric forms, so the IUPAC proposed
310 InChI(Heller et al., 2013) as an alternative solution. These string-based molecular representations have
311 become the most commonly used data representation methods in sequence-based deep learning.

312 **Language modeling**

313 Researchers are increasingly interested in exploring how to use concepts from natural language processing
314 to solve chemical problems(Ozturk et al., 2020). The algorithms commonly used in chemical language
315 models are RNNs and Transformers(Bagal et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2021). Arranging atoms or amino acids
316 (symbols) into structures to produce molecules and biological functions is similar to composing words and
317 sentences with letters to define the meaning of text (Fig. 5)(Grechishnikova, 2021). When processing
318 biochemical sequences, chemical language models help to explore the vast chemical space
319 effectively(Honda et al., 2019; Meng et al., 2022). Language models are suitable for dealing with biological
320 sequences such as protein sequences and toxic relationships or interactions between organisms and
321 chemicals.

322

323 RNN and their variants can capture high-dimensional molecular features such as physicochemical(Gupta et
324 al., 2018; Segler et al., 2018) and biological properties(Grisoni et al., 2018; Merk, Friedrich, et al., 2018;
325 Merk, Grisoni, et al., 2018; W. Yuan et al., 2017) by learning SMILES(Segler et al., 2018) representation
326 (semantics). RNN has been applied to molecular feature extraction(Gomez-Bombarelli et al., 2018),
327 showing that the learned features are superior to traditional molecular descriptors and graph convolution
328 methods in virtual screening and property prediction. For example, Lin(Lin et al., 2020) set up a BiGRU
329 model to learn SMILES character information for toxicity prediction on Tox21, SIDER and ClinTox dataset,
330 and the results showed that the model performed better than classical graph-structured methods. Consistent
331 result can be obtained by Peng(Peng et al., 2019 iee international conference on bioinformatics and
332 biomedicine (bibt/2019) when researching on molecule toxicity prediction, BiGRU model for molecular
333 representation learning could defeat three baseline machine learning models and five classical methods. In

334 Preuer's work(Preuer et al., 2018), the molecular similarity measuring method called Fréchet ChemNet
335 distance has become the reference method via learning of physicochemical and biological features by RNN.
336
337 Likewise, Transformers-based approach have been applied to molecular property prediction(Chithrananda
338 et al., 2020; Grechishnikova, 2021; Meng et al., 2022) and optimization(J. He et al., 2021) and have shown
339 superior performance over traditional features(Zheng et al., 2019). A recent example in the field of
340 molecular toxicity prediction highlights the success of using transformer architecture for chemical toxicity
341 prediction(Gustavsson et al., 2024). The study utilized RoBERTa to directly read SMILES strings,
342 capturing features related to toxicity from the chemical structures. It demonstrated high performance in
343 predicting the toxicity for algae, aquatic invertebrates, and fish, surpassing traditional QSAR methods. The
344 model is not limited to specific chemical categories and can process all chemical structures included in the
345 training set, showing broader applicability and lower prediction errors compared to traditional QSAR
346 methods. It is important to emphasize that the unique self-attention mechanism feature extractor in the
347 transformer is key to the enhanced performance of this series of models and provides logical inference for
348 the model. Another example illustrated by Norinder(Norinder, 2023) also state that the MolBERT model
349 get slightly high values of sensitivity, specificity and accuracy compared with RF on binary non-toxic and
350 very-toxic CATMoS datasets. The innovation of this technology will offer strong support in terms of
351 reducing animal testing, screening a large number of chemical substances rapidly, and developing safer
352 chemical products.

353

354 **3.4 Limitations for deep representation learning**

355 GNN and language models both play a role in automatically extracting features from chemical structures.

356 Therefore, the quality of feature learning directly impacts the model's performance. This term is also
357 known as "embeddings". Nevertheless, automatic feature learning would bring several issues for model.
358 The first issue is whether graph convolutional layer or encoder, they map molecules to high-dimensional
359 spaces through non-linear transformations, which often losing human interpretability and physical meaning.
360 Consequently, it becomes difficult to discern whether the model or the embeddings has truly learned
361 meaningful knowledge. We can only rely on the metrics results to evaluate the model. The second issue is
362 in order to improve predictive performance, excessive layer stacking is a common method to used to extract
363 high-dimensional features sometimes. However, it would lead to increasingly "black-box" models,
364 reducing its interpretability and confidence. The third issue is the increase of model complexity and
365 redundancy would have resource-intensive training because of adding more layers.

366

367 **4. The emerging training strategy for embeddings improvements to enhance molecule toxicity** 368 **prediction**

369 Data scientists and AI researchers have developed a series of methods to enhance embeddings(Bengio,
370 2012), including self-supervised learning(Fang et al., 2022), contrastive learning(Y. Wang et al., 2022), and
371 multi-task learning (Table 1, Fig. 6). Since the transformer architecture invent in 2017, the self-attention
372 mechanism rapidly gained popularity(Vaswani et al., Advances in neural information processing systems 30
373 (nips 2017)/2017). However, this powerful model requires high-quality and large-scale training data, which
374 sometimes need several gigabytes or even tens of gigabytes of data to achieve optimal results. Therefore,
375 self-supervised learning methods have been adopted to pre-trained the parameters in the larger corpus to
376 alleviate the problem of downstream data deficiencies that is a common occurrence in reality(Bengio,
377 2012). This method can leverage a large amount of unlabeled data to form a pre-trained model that captures

378 semantic information, which can then be fine-tuned on small data sets for various downstream tasks. And it
379 have been proved by the unprecedented performance of Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) language
380 models(Achiam et al., 2023). As a result, self-supervised learning of Large language models (LLMs)
381 receiving much attention and also applied in chemical pre-trained models to improve molecule embeddings.
382 The resulting embedding enhanced the prediction performance of downstream supervised tasks and enabled
383 similar compounds to have similar vector representations. It is important to note that this
384 pre-training-fine-tuning paradigm (Transfer learning) has outperformed the traditional ab initio supervised
385 training method in some tasks.

386

387 In the early stage, self-supervised learning methods, such as word2vec, were used to learn
388 high-dimensional semantic features in early NLP (Natural Language Processing) research. Mol2vec(Jaeger
389 et al., 2018) and Prot2vec(Asgari & Mofrad, 2015) extended this approach to obtain the embedding of
390 high-dimensional substructures and n-grams of protein sequences, which enabled similar compounds to
391 have similar vector representations. While in the post-transformer era, masked language modeling is a
392 widely used method for self-supervised learning of natural language and biological sequences, which aims
393 to recover the masked tokens in a sequence using the bidirectional sequence context. Morozov(Morozov et
394 al., 2023) fine-tuned ProteinBERT model to identify toxic protein and peptide based solely on amino acid
395 sequence with 2475 toxic and 214,740 non-toxic sequences obtained from UniProt. The model performance
396 exceeds CSM-Toxin and ToxinPred2 with MCC of 0.64 and an AUC of 0.86 on test dataset. Hu compared
397 different pre-training self-supervised strategies in terms of node level and graph level on Tox21, ToxCast,
398 ClinTox for four types of GNN. The experimental results show that GIN model is the most expressive one
399 with pre-training of context prediction, gaining average 4.1%, 2.3%, 14.6% ROC-AUC on three toxicity

400 dataset mentioned above, respectively. These kind of examples prove that the self-supervised learning
401 based pre-training techniques could enhanced the the learning and expression ability of deep neural
402 network associate with parameter initialization, model regularization, and generalization capabilities.

403

404 Additionally, other training strategy such as contrastive learning can also improve the representation ability
405 of data. Wang(H. Wang et al., 2023) introduced molecular graph contrastive learning as preprocess to fulfill
406 molecular similarities characterization, which futher boost GAT performance by changing latent
407 representation on 15 end point envrionmental datasets. Li(J.-C. Li, 2020) trained multi-task learning NN on
408 tox21 data, showing that the model can share common information among task to produce reliable forecast
409 even encountered the issue of imbalanced data. Jain(Jain et al., 2021) used multi-task learning to build a
410 consensus model among multispecies for acute toxicity prediction. Chen(J. Chen et al., 2021) proposed
411 GCN via Mean Teacher semi-supervised learning algorithm to learn unannotated data on Tox21 data for
412 chemical toxicity prediction. Feinstein(Feinstein et al., 2021) developed a transfer-learned model by
413 retrieving all organic compounds for oral rat LD50 from public datasets, embedded in SelectiveNet
414 architecture to predict PFAS toxicity. Schlender(Schlender et al., 2023) established The Bigger Fish
415 framework, which employs a meta-learning strategy to tackle the few-shot problem in aquatic toxicity.
416 These techniques have already demonstrated their success in the field of molecular property prediction with
417 numerous examples, including drug ADMET prediction(X. Yang et al., 2019). In the field of data science,
418 they play a crucial role in addressing bias embeddings, model generalization and data scarcity. They are
419 gradually penetrating into environmental ecotoxicity prediction from now on, although there is still much
420 exploration to be done (Table 3) (Chakravarti & Alla, 2019; Y. Chen et al., 2023; Ketkar et al., 2023; S. Li
421 et al., 2021; J. Zhang et al., 2021).

422

423 **5. Common public database for model evaluation**

424 The role of all public datasets is that they can be used to evaluate or train new machine learning models.

425 Therefore, after developers propose a new model framework, it is best to evaluate its performance on

426 public datasets to obtain the most accurate assessment of the model and to convince users of its reliability.

427 The following is a summary of commonly used datasets for the development of toxicity machine learning

428 models.

429 *Tox21*: The Toxicology in the 21st Century (Tox21) program aimed to assess the potential toxicity of

430 chemicals to human health, which is a high-throughput toxicity evaluation initiative and attract scientific

431 community to develop various computational methods to give alternative solutions for the experiments of

432 in vitro and in vivo testing.

433 *Toxcast*: U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) also proposed Toxicity Forecaster (ToxCast)

434 program in 2007 to advocate assessment of hazard chemicals. These assays utilize various technologies to

435 assess the impact of chemical exposure on a wide range of biological targets across nearly 10,000

436 substances.

437 *ClinTox*: The ClinTox dataset, created by John S. Brownstein and colleagues in 2014, was developed to

438 address the challenge of predicting drug toxicity and clinical approval status. It integrates information from

439 multiple public databases, including chemical structures of drugs and clinical trial outcomes, providing a

440 valuable resource for drug safety assessment.

441

442 However, those datasets are incomplete datasets, with gaps in data for certain compounds and an imbalance

443 in chemical classes, which may affect the performance and generalizability of predictive models. Although

444 these datasets contain rich chemical information, biological experimental data, and detection information,
445 the data has been simplified to include only SMILES strings and binary classification labels. This
446 significant simplification means that the models do not learn the target information, which is detrimental to
447 establishing models based on toxicity mechanisms. Additionally, the labels in the data may not represent
448 the true ground truth. A study has shown that within the tested concentration range, approximately half of
449 the chemicals exhibit cytotoxicity (Judson et al., 2016). Therefore, a large portion of the observed activity
450 may be due to assay interference caused by cytotoxicity. It is necessary to confirm whether the observed
451 activity is related to specific biomolecular interactions (true positives) or confounded by cytotoxicity (false
452 positives). Since cytotoxicity information is not considered in these datasets, models built on such data may
453 be biased.

454

455 **6. Overview of interpretable method for deep learning**

456 While having highly accurate models is important, the interpretability analysis of models is a crucial aspect
457 for their practical application. In this section, we review commonly used interpretability algorithms in
458 current toxicity machine learning models, taking Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME)
459 and SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) algorithms as examples. We also introduce interpretability
460 algorithms for deep learning models based on other algorithmic principles, along with their underlying
461 principles and mature software frameworks, to help developers and users understand the model
462 decision-making process. Given the different taxonomies of interpretability algorithms in the fields of GNN,
463 CNN, and LLM, we adopt the post-hoc and self-interpretable taxonomy here.

464 **6.1 Post-hoc Method**

465 Post-hoc interpretation methods are techniques used to explain model predictions after the model has been

466 trained. These methods do not require access to the model's internal structure or feature representations and
467 can be applied to various types of models. Commonly used methods such as LIME, SHAP, and Sensitivity
468 Analysis (SA) fall under the category of feature attribution as explanation and are model-agnostic post-hoc
469 interpretation methods.

470 **6.1.1 Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations**

471 The LIME method, also known as the Approximation or Surrogate method, aims to learn an interpretable
472 model (i.e., a surrogate model) to approximate the output of a black-box model. Specifically, for a given x ,
473 LIME attempts to find a potentially interpretable model g (such as a linear model or decision tree) as a local
474 explanation. Its expression is as follows $g_x = \arg \min_{g \in G} L(f, g, \pi_x) + \Omega(g)$, where f is the model to
475 be explained, π_x is the kernel function representing the distance measure between the input x and the
476 generated neighboring samples x' , L is the loss function measuring the fidelity between f and g , G is the set
477 of candidate interpretable models, Ω is the complexity penalty of g , ensuring g remains interpretable. For
478 instance, Nascimento (Nascimento et al., 2023) used LIME to identify toxic structural alerts with more than
479 6 heavy atoms. Cicek (Balikci Cicek et al., 2023) used it to determine the biomark of lncRNAs for
480 nephrotoxicity. LIME package are public available in (<https://github.com/marcotcr/lime>)

481

482 **6.1.2 SHapley Additive exPlanations**

483 The SHAP method originates from game theory and aims to solve the problem of distributing the total
484 gains generated by a coalition of all players to each player based on their individual contributions. Due to
485 its strong theoretical foundation, it has been widely applied in the field of machine learning interpretability
486 and has gradually been used to explain toxicological machine learning models as the field has developed.
487 For a coalition game, the Shapley value is a solution to the problem of gain distribution. The idea is to

488 determine the average contribution of feature i to the prediction result by calculating its marginal
489 contribution in different feature subsets. The contribution (attribution) of feature i can be calculated as
490 follows $\phi_i = \frac{1}{|N|} \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} \binom{|N|-1}{|S|} (\nu(S \cup \{i\}) - \nu(S))$, where N is the set of all features, $|N|$ is the
491 number of features in the set, S is a subset of features, $|S|$ is the number of features in the subset, $\nu(S)$ is
492 the model output using only the subset S , and $\nu(S \cup \{i\})$ is the model output using the subset S and
493 feature i . $(\nu(S \cup \{i\}) - \nu(S))$ represents the marginal contribution of feature i to subset S . By using SHAP,
494 Lou (Lou et al., 2024) identified important features and structural fragments associated with acute dermal
495 toxicity and Lysenko (Lysenko et al., 2018) select the feature to relate idiosyncratic toxic subset. SHAP
496 algorithm are public available in (<https://github.com/shap/shap>).

497

498 **6.1.3 Sensitive Analysis**

499 Sensitivity analysis (SA) is commonly used in mathematical modeling and statistical methods and can also
500 be employed to assess feature importance. Specifically, it measures the extent of change in the model
501 output by altering one or more input features. Common algorithms include the One-At-a-Time (OAT)
502 method, Sobol method (Sobol', 1993), and Morris method (Morris, 1991). However, sensitivity analysis
503 relies to some extent on the analyst's assumptions about the range of parameter changes, which may
504 introduce subjectivity. It typically considers the variation of individual parameters, potentially overlooking
505 the interaction effects between multiple parameters. As the dimensionality of features increases, sensitivity
506 analysis requires substantial computational resources. For example, Carriger (Carriger et al., 2016) used SA
507 in Bayesian network to evaluate the feature associate with chemical modes of action of aquatic toxicology.

508

509 **6.1.4 Other interpretable method used in deep learning**

510 In post-hoc interpretation methods for feature attribution, using gradients to explain individual model
511 decisions is a natural idea, as gradients represent the 'direction' and rate of the fastest increase in the loss
512 function, making them well-suited for the backpropagation mechanism in deep learning. Therefore,
513 gradient-based interpretability methods are primarily used to explain the predictions of complex models,
514 such as neural networks. By calculating the gradient of the model output with respect to the input features,
515 the importance of each feature to the prediction result can be assessed and the larger the gradient value, the
516 greater the feature's impact on the prediction.

517

518 Common methods include Guided Backpropagation (Springenberg et al., 2014), Integrated Gradients
519 (Sundararajan et al., 2017), SmoothGrad (Smilkov et al., 2017), and Gradient-weighted Class Activation
520 Mapping (Grad-CAM) (Selvaraju et al., 2017). These methods have also been used to interpret DL toxicity
521 model (Samek et al., 2019; Webel et al., 2020) . Preuer (Preuer et al., 2019) adopted Integrated Gradients
522 method to extract toxicophores from tox21. In addition to gradient-based methods, commonly used
523 interpretability algorithms for GNN models include GNNExplainer (Ying et al., 2019), PGExplainer (Luo
524 et al., 2020), PGMEExplainer, and GraphLime. Ahn (Ahn et al., 2024) propose XplainScreen framework
525 including GNNExplainer, Layerwise Relevance Propagation, DeepLIFT, GradCAM to show that the ability
526 of virtual screening tasks based on toxicity. Wang (Y. Wang et al., 2023) evaluate several interpret methods
527 on acute oral toxicity, presenting that integrated gradient have better attribution performance. Since
528 interpretability is not the main topic of our work, and there exists a kingdom of algorithms in the
529 Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) domain, for a detailed explanation and algorithm principle of
530 these new methods, please refer to the relevant work (Kakkad et al., 2023; Y. Zhang et al., 2021). More

531 well-established interprete package could find in PyG(https://github.com/pyg-team/pytorch_geometric),
532 iNNvestigate(<https://github.com/albermax/innvestigate>),
533 InterpretML(<https://github.com/interpretml/interpret>),
534 OpenXAI(<https://github.com/AI4LIFE-GROUP/OpenXAI>), Captum for pytorch
535 (<https://github.com/pytorch/captum>), Eli5 (<https://github.com/eli5-org/eli5>).

536

537 **6.2 Self-interpretable Method**

538 Compared to post-hoc interpretation algorithms, the models with global interpretability are more likely to
539 be favored by users. The structure and decision-making process of these models are intuitive and easy to
540 understand, without the need for additional interpretative tools or methods to comprehend their outputs. For
541 example, the weight parameters and explicit expressions of linear models, or the decision logic of decision
542 trees, can be clearly visualized. These models are globally self-interpretable. However, these models with
543 clear expressions and easily understandable equations may struggle to capture hidden nonlinear
544 relationships in the data, often resulting in lower performance compared to black-box models. This
545 necessitates a trade-off between model developers and users based on specific application scenarios.

546

547 **7. Discussion**

548 With the continuous innovation in artificial intelligence technology, environmental scientists have also
549 incorporated this technology into their research and claim to have utilized AI models in their work. But you
550 might ask, “what is meanings of artificial intelligence?” The International Business Machines Corporation
551 (IBM) have classed artificial intelligence into weak AI and strong AI(Flowers, 2019). Specifically, weak AI
552 is “AI trained and focused to perform specific tasks whereas strong AI or general AI have self-aware with a

553 consciousness that would have the ability to solve problems, learn, and plan for the future.” In other words,
554 allowing machines to autonomously learn and make decisions, without human intervention, is a
555 manifestation of greater intelligence. That is the reason why current deep learning technologies are
556 gradually moving away from the heavy reliance on expert feature engineering that was prevalent before in
557 CV and NLP. In this case, the next promising trend for QSAR modeling will also towards the development
558 of more general artificial intelligence, that is the trend from feature engineering to deep representation
559 learning specifically(McGibbon et al., 2024).

560

561 The feature engineering based methods have been successful in various toxicity prediction tasks. They have
562 the characteristic of flexible, physical meanings, fast calculation supported by free package and webserver
563 (user-friendly), incorporation expert knowledge etc, which are well famous molecule featurization way for
564 environmental and chemistry modelers. The models that receive these inputs tend to be easy to interpret
565 such as polynomial regression or RF, the coefficients or the decision conditions of each tree could reflect
566 the decision process of the QSAR model, respectively, which is significantly important for the research area
567 that already have prior knowledge. But they still suffered from some challenges and it’s hard to overcome:
568 ①They require expert knowledge and much effort to design different features that are suitable for different
569 tasks. ②The vector is high-dimensional and sparse, and cannot capture molecular similarity and handle
570 “Activity cliffs”. ③Modelers have to stack and evaluate thousands of descriptors as more and more MDs
571 and FPs have been developed.

572

573 By contrast, deep representation learning, however, has the potential to solve the above problems to some
574 extent. They use sequential layers to extract higher-level and dense representations of data without human

575 intervention and learns patterns from the dataset to predict future behaviors, which take a step towards
576 intelligence. When encountering the issue of activity cliffs, the model automatically adjusts the learned
577 molecular embeddings based on the labels through the loss function. Furthermore, when the model can
578 extract information from the molecular encodings across more diverse dimensions, as refer to hybrid model
579 later, it can further overcome such issues. Also it is reported that a model with strong generalization ability
580 can be trained by fine-tuning a pre-trained model via transfer learning when faced with a small size labeled
581 dataset. By following this strategy, the research team can share their models and feature analyses as an
582 initial iteration for subsequent related datasets. This approach partially alleviates the need to generate large
583 datasets from scratch for training models, reduces redundant work, and fosters a positive workflow in the
584 field of toxicity modeling.

585
586 By using summarized encode formats, machine learning models and deep learning models serve as
587 fundamental units or backbone, developers combine them like building “LEGO” blocks to explore the
588 potential performance of different input formats and model combinations, leading to the emergence of
589 hybrid and multimodal models. For example, Sharma (Sharma et al., 2022) used a self-collected dataset to
590 explore the performance of descriptor-based, fingerprint-based, and hybrid-based encoding formats in
591 random forest, multi-linear regression, and partial least squares regression models, with experimental
592 results showing similar accuracy, achieving an accuracy of 0.93. Limbu (Limbu et al., 2022) developed the
593 HNN-Tox model, a combination of CNN and MLP models, with an AUROC of 0.89. Liu (J. Liu et al.,
594 2023) combined BiGRU and GraphSAGE to learn the SMILES representation and molecular structure,
595 outperforming the baseline model on the Tox21 dataset. Karim (Karim et al., 2019) explored multiple
596 heterogeneous neural network types and different data representations, training FC, CNN, RNN, and their

597 fused multimodal model MNN on the IGC50 dataset, achieving an R2 of 0.86 on the test set. Zhao (Zhao et
598 al., 2024) embedded descriptors to build a GCN-enhanced model with 213,084 substances to screen PMT
599 substances through feature fusion. In summary, these techniques follow the principle of using different
600 models to learn from various encoding formats (hand-crafted, graph, SMILES, image, etc.) and then
601 combining them through feature fusion. Various studies indicate that, despite potentially increasing
602 computational costs and data dependency, this “LEGO” building block approach is effective in terms of
603 performance.

604

605 Nevertheless, deep learning or hybrid model brings higher predictive performance, it still has some
606 drawbacks that should be overcome in the future. One is they require more computational resources and
607 training data to pretrain feature encoder and their complex network structure make the model difficult to
608 interpret compared to QSAR methods. They have huge potential ability to learn complex patterns and
609 relationships from data, but they may also capture hidden biases or errors that are hard to detect. Therefore,
610 deep learning models need to be interpretable and validated by checking whether their decision-making
611 processes match the expert knowledge or generate new insights. The interpretation methods we
612 summarized could somewhat enhance the reliability of deep learning models, but they do not fully
613 elucidate the decision-making process of the models. We recommend that ① For critical scenarios where
614 interpretability is essential or where incorrect model decisions could lead to significant incidents, it is best
615 to use self-interpretable ‘white-box’ models such as linear regression. ② For scenarios where model
616 accuracy is more important, deep learning models or hybrid are recommended if computation cost are
617 affordable. Also if post-hoc methods are required to interpret these models, it is important to note that some
618 of them are surrogate model and the explanations provided may be different. Additionally, interpretability

619 methods are not robust and can be easily manipulated to produce any desired explanation (Slack et al.,
620 2020). In such cases, it is advisable to use multiple methods for comparison and repeated testing. A
621 common pitfall in deep learning interpretability is that people tend to choose explanations they can
622 understand, but these may not reflect the model's true decision logic. Therefore, even with these post-hoc
623 interpretability methods, the deep model is only turn to 'grey' rather than 'white'.

624
625 Another promising field for deep representation learning is data augmentation, which is used to generate
626 uniformly distributed data in whole data sets to mitigate data deficiency. In January 2018,
627 Gomez-Bombarelli(Gomez-Bombarelli et al., 2018) published the first implementation of a continuous and
628 reversible molecular representation learned by a computer using a VAE structure, where molecules are
629 encoded by using a neural network (NN) to convert their SMILES strings into continuous value vectors. In
630 Gomez-Bombarelli's experiments, the authors trained 250,000 drug-like small molecules, creating a
631 chemical latent space for small molecule exploration. This latent space is convenient for downstream tasks,
632 when it is connected to a decoder, it can be used for generation tasks, and when it is connected to a
633 classifier, it can be used for physical and chemical property prediction tasks (Fig 7). This technology has
634 significant application potential in addressing insufficient toxicological data and could be controlled by
635 reinforcement learning in the future(Bjerrum et al., 2023; Olivecrona et al., 2017).

636
637 From our perspective, although the automatic feature extraction capability of deep learning brings great
638 convenience, it is unlikely to completely replace feature engineering. Despite of chemical structure
639 representation, feature engineering is very flexible and can handle a variety of data formats, including
640 continuous, discrete variables, experiment condition, end-point method, target information etc. While deep

641 learning techniques are tailored to specific encoding formats. For particular task we want to establish a
642 data-driven model, we recommend focus on the size of the data we have obtained. And according to the
643 rule of thumb in data science and generalization bound of machine learning theory (Abu-Mostafa et al.,
644 2012), at least 10 data points are needed to fit one parameter. Therefore, with around 1,000 data points,
645 classical machine learning models and shallow deep learning models can be considered. As the amount of
646 data grows, exploring deeper or hybrid models becomes feasible. For datasets with a few hundred data
647 points, simple QSAR models or decision trees are the first choice due to their self-interpretability and
648 generalizability. Another option is to fine-tune pre-trained models on your small dataset. Although it is
649 generally accepted that fine-tuning downstream supervised tasks via pre-trained models is better than
650 directly building supervised learning models in the AI domain, this approach still needs more validation
651 and exploration in toxicity or environmental datasets. However, the application of these techniques requires
652 finding pre-trained models relevant to your task.

653

654 We anticipate that feature engineering and automated feature extraction methods will be interdependent.
655 Deep representation learning alleviates the cumbersome construction process of feature engineering, while
656 feature engineering complements representation learning by incorporating expert knowledge that has not
657 been learned. Some examples concluded that fuse descriptor-based feature with deep learning feature could
658 boost model performance, through of which probably it is not necessary for model pretraining. Li(X. Li et
659 al., 2023) claimed current pre-training approach face the challenge of node-level auxiliary learning would
660 have biased knowledge. Hence, Descriptor-based Graph Self-supervised Learning model have been
661 proposed to overcome this challenge. It embed human interpretable rich local subgraph information to
662 achieves SOTA performance on three toxicity-related benchmarks. Through this approach of feature fusion,

663 GNN could not only extract dense embeddings for latent space for sepcific mission but also adopt
664 descriptor feature from expert knowledge to make reliable decision. This is resonable to embed expert
665 knowledge correlate with prediction tasks into features to enhance model decision-making capability.

666

667 **8. Future outlook and environmental implication**

668 QSAR-based toxicity prediction models can help overcome the limitations of animal testing and offer
669 alternative approaches in chemical management. This review analyzes the molecular representation
670 methods and algorithms used in recent toxicity prediction research based on chemical structures. This work
671 suggests that deep learning-based QSAR models show promise as alternatives to traditional models.
672 Traditional QSAR models have limitations, such as the 'activity cliff' problem and limited data availability.
673 Therefore, exploring new methods to address these issues is essential. Currently, efforts are underway to
674 enhance model predictive performance using various algorithms based on the concept of AI, including
675 supervised, self-supervised, transfer learning and multi-task learning. However, the emergence of these new
676 methods brings a series of problems.

677

678 Firstly, Public datasets are crucial for fair model comparisons, avoiding data heterogeneity issues. Most
679 articles build their models using self-collected toxicity data, employing similar methods, which is not
680 meaningful because the comparisons are not parallel. We cannot determine whether the performance
681 improvements of the new model are due to data heterogeneity, model structure, or other factors. For
682 self-collected toxicity data, we recommend first using a baseline model or other publications' model to
683 obtain metrics (e.g., R^2 for regression). Then, report the performance improvements achieved by your
684 newly developed model. It would be beneficial to include details about your model's parameters and the

685 runtime. Also reporting performance on public datasets for extra work is benefits for transparency and
686 reproducibility in research. It allows others to verify results and build upon the work, enhancing the overall
687 confidence in the model's capabilities. Alternatively, for model structure methodology studies, we strongly
688 recommend using public datasets like Tox21 and ToxCast as mentioned in this work. Only by comparing
689 models using the same dataset, following the control variate method, can we obtain convincing
690 experimental results. Standardizing model development processes is also crucial for achieving trustworthy
691 results, which is achievable at the current stage (J.-J. Zhu et al., 2023).

692
693 Secondly, the black-box nature of deep learning models limits the scientific explanations behind prediction
694 results, making them challenging for regulatory applications in chemical management. While deep learning
695 techniques can improve model performance, they lack of confidence without clear explanations for the
696 decision-making process, which masks it difficult to trust the results and limit their practical use.
697 Developers need to balance the trade-off between model performance and interpretability, as well as
698 scientific reliability. Capturing hidden biased patterns in predictions is not low probability event in deep
699 learning. Thus, it is important to note that models grounded in reliable scientific expert knowledge are more
700 valuable than those with simply good performance.

701
702 Furthermore, many toxicity prediction models in research rely on proprietary algorithms and technologies,
703 with few source codes made publicly available. This hinders readers' ability to assess the reproducibility of
704 experiments and compare models, making it difficult to evaluate the results presented by the authors. We
705 recommend that models be published with open-source code or that online prediction platforms be
706 established for broader evaluation and use.

707

708 In the context of the growing awareness of artificial intelligence, toxicity models based on deep
709 representation learning are increasingly leading in predictive performance. However, traditional QSAR
710 models still dominate in terms of reliability and practical application. The main limitation of these
711 high-performance AI models is their lack of interpretability. Future work should aim to better connect these
712 models with toxicity mechanisms to develop more reliable and accurate toxicity prediction models, as this
713 is crucial for both environmental and social benefits. As it can reduce the need for animal testing by
714 accurately predicting the toxicity of chemicals and drugs, which also aligns with ethical standards and
715 promotes corporate social responsibility. Additionally, improved toxicity predictions help in identifying and
716 regulating potentially hazardous substances before they enter the environment. These may also help
717 environmental protection agency to regulate industrial emission, thereby preventing pollution and
718 protecting ecosystems. Moreover, it could help identify harmful substances at the early stages of chemical
719 development, reducing the risk of public exposure to toxic substances and improving public health as well
720 as generating economic benefits.

721

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Table 1
Glossary
<p>KNN (k-Nearest Neighbor) is a method that selects the K training samples x_i ($i=1,2,\dots,k$) that are closest to the input sample x_0, and assigns them weights w_i based on the inverse proportion of their distances to the input samples. Then, it sums up the weights of each class and estimates the probability of the input sample belonging to each class by dividing the class weight by the</p> $P_{C_n} = \frac{\sum_{j \in C_n} W_j}{\sum_{i=1}^k W_i}, (n = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ <p>total weight. The formula is</p> <p>SVM (Support vector machine) aims to find the unique optimal hyperplane that separates the data into different classes and identifies the support vectors that are the closest points to the boundary from each class. The objective is to maximize the distance between these points and the boundary. Using the Lagrange multiplier method, we can formulate the objective function as follows</p> $\max_{\alpha} [\min_{w,b} L(w, b, \alpha)] = \max_{\alpha} [\min_{w,b} (\frac{1}{2} \ w\ ^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i (y_i (w \cdot x_i + b) - 1))] , \text{ where } w$ <p>and b that satisfy the above equation are the solution of SVM.</p> <p>The principle of Decision Tree and Random Forest is to maximize the information gain, such as Gini impurity $\sum_{i=1}^C f_i(1-f_i)$, the input x is recursively assigned to child nodes based on this criterion. Random forest is an ensemble model that integrates many decision trees and uses a voting mechanism to determine the final classification result.</p> <p>Bayesian Algorithms are methods of statistical inference that use Bayes theorem to update the probability of a hypothesis based on prior knowledge and observed data. For a given $x = (x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots, x^{(n)})$, the probability that the data belongs to c, because the denominator can be considered as a constant, therefore,</p> $p(Y = c X = x) = \frac{p(X = x Y = c)p(Y = c)}{p(X = x)}$ <p>$f(x) = \arg \max_c p(Y = c X = x) = \arg \max_c p(X = x Y = c)p(Y = c)$. And naive Bayes</p>

is a method based on Bayes' theorem and feature conditional independence assumption to

$$p(X = x | Y = c)p(Y = c) \approx \prod_{i=1}^k p(X = x_i | Y = c)$$

simplify the calculation

GBDT (Gradient Boosting Decision Tree) is the result of weak learners decision trees sequentially building, composed of Regression Decision Tree, Gradient Boosting, Shrinkage,

$$f_M(x) = \sum_{m=1}^M T(x; \theta_m),$$

where T is the decision tree, θ_m is the parameter, and M is the number

of trees.

ANN (Artificial Neural Networks) consists of a collection of artificial neurons that are connected to each other and serve as the basic units of information processing. Each neuron can

be mathematically represented by $y = \sigma(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b)$, where σ denotes the activation function.

RNN (Recurrent Neural Network) are a type of artificial neural network architecture for recognizing patterns in sequential data. RNNs introduce concatenated units that can consider not only the current state x^t but also the past state x^{t-1} , with the expression $S^t = \sigma(Wx^t + US^{t-1})$, where σ is the activation function, W is the weight matrix, and U is the hidden state to hidden state matrix (i.e., transition matrix). RNNs are prone to problems such as gradient vanishing, so different variants such as LSTM and GRU have been developed to solve this problem.

CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) consists of a bunch of convolutional modules for feature extraction, followed by one or more fully connected layers for prediction and loss minimization. This processing architecture is commonly used for image processing problems, and a schematic diagram is shown in Fig 1. Convolutional layers are described by their width, height and depth, aggregating information from individual receptive fields in the x and y directions, and depth z can represent the dimension of information (in images it is RGB color).

GNN (Graph Neural Networks) is usually used to deal with graph data problems, learning to encode the hidden layer representation of local graph structure and node features, and its

hierarchical propagation rules follow $H^{(l+1)} = \sigma(\tilde{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{A} \tilde{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}} H^{(l)} W^{(l)})$ (Fig. 2).

VAE (Variational Autoencoder) is a deep generative model that can learn latent stochastic representations from data and use them to generate new data. VAE consists of an encoder and a decoder, the encoder maps the input data to a latent space, the decoder samples from the latent space and reconstructs the input data.

Transformer is a neural system architecture that uses attention mechanism to parallel process sequential data through a series of steps. It extracts data features through modules such as multi-head, residual connection, position encoding, etc. to form new representations.

Reinforcement Learning agents interact with the environment to choose the optimal actions that produce the maximum expected cumulative reward.

Self-supervised Learning, is a strategy to train on unlabeled datasets without manual labels. It learns from the data itself by predicting the masked part from the rest of the raw data.

Contrastive Learning can be considered as a kind of self-supervised learning, which distinguishes similar samples from dissimilar ones.

Transfer Learning is used to train in the source domain, and then use the knowledge extracted from the source domain is used to accelerate learning in the target domain.

Multi-task learning involves predicting multiple tasks at the same time, based on similar tasks that share common parameters or priors. This way, it can capture the inherent correlation among different data sources. The main challenge of multi-task learning is how to filter out irrelevant information, so that the performance of each task is not affected by others.

Meta-learning is a machine learning method that “learns to learn” by updating model parameters on the support set and evaluating model performance on the query set. Meta-learning enables the model to acquire a kind of “prior knowledge”, and quickly learn new tasks based on the existing “knowledge”.

1148 Table 2 Summary of recent advances in molecular toxicity prediction using molecular descriptors and fingerprints

Target of prediction	Methods	Features	Data sources	Performance report	Ref
Persistent, mobile, and toxic substances/very persistent and mobile substances	SVM, KNN, GaussianNB, logistic regression (LR), RF, GBDT, XGBoost, light gradient boosting machine (LightGBM), artificial neural network (ANN)	207 MDs	PubChem	AUROC > 0.951	Zhao et.al
Pesticide toxicity against aquatic organism	C4.5 decision tree (DT), NB, KNN, RF, SVM	8MDs, 7FPs	PPDB, PAN	ACC = 0.848	He et.al
Persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic of persistent organic pollutants	DCNN	2424 MDs	EU REACH, US EPA TSCA, Stockholm Convention, Canada DSL	ACC= 95.3 ± 0.6%, F=79.3 ± 2.5%	Sun et.al
Predicting the ecotoxicity of unidentified chemicals in water	xgboost	6 FPs	CompTox	RMSE=0.89	Peets et.al
Carcinogenic prediction of hazardous organic chemicals	RF, LR, SVM, NB, KNN, XGBoost, Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)	1444 MDs	Inventory of Hazardous Chemicals, GHS	ACC = 1	Hao et.al
Toxicity	k-DNN, BNB, kNN, RF, SVM	1024 FCFPs	ToxCast/Tox21	AUC = 0.864–0.927	Ciallella et.al

Identify potential ligands of AhR	RF, DNN	2048 ECFP2	ToxCast/Tox21/personal data	precision rate = 0.96 recall rate = 0.64	Zhu et.al
Evaluate new toxicants	xgboost	Mordred	Tox21	AUC=0.683-0.9	Kurosaki et.al
Screen pesticides for estrogen receptor (ER) agonistic activity	RF, DNN	ECFP2	Tox21	-	Shen et.al
Screen chemicals for fish toxicity	RF	2757 MDs and FPs	OASIS, ECOTOX, EAT5, NORMAN SusDat	ACC = 0.73	Samanipour et.al
C-F bond dissociation energy	RF, Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator Rgression (LASSO), FFNN	C-F bond descriptors	Self-collected	Deviations less than 0.70 kcal/mol	Raza et al
Bioactivities of PFASs	k-means, DBSCAN, Hierarchical DBSCAN	ECFP4	PubChem's BioAssay, Maximum Unbiased Validation, Tox21, beta-secretase 1, blood-brain barrier penetration datasets	Accuracy=0.973	Kwon et al.

Table 3 Summary of recent advances in molecular toxicity prediction using deep representation learning

Target of prediction	Traning Strategy	Model	Data sources	Best model performance report	Ref
The effect of Exogenous Chemicals on Virus Receptor Gene Transcription	Supervised learning	GCN	Self-collected	AUROC=0.7 on test	Liu et al. 2023
Public toxic database	Supervised learning	GCN	Tox21	AUROC=0.734	Zhang et al. 2021
Ecotoxicology	Supervised learning	GNN (Attentive FP)	Self-collected from literature	Average R ² =0.65	Ketkar et al.2023
hERG-blocking property of compounds	Supervised learning	GCN	Two publications and ChEMBL	AUROC=0.952	Chen et al. 2023
Mutagenicity prediction	Supervised learning	GCN	Ames mutagenicity benchmark dataset	AUROC=0.83-0.87	Li et al. 2020
Persistent, bio-accumulative, and toxic substances	Supervised learning	GAT	Self-collected from multi database	AUROC=97.9, PR=89.7, ACC=93.8	Wang et al.2022
Ecotoxicology	Supervised learning	GraphSAGE	EnviroTox	AUROC=0.91, AUPRC=0.95	Anand et al.2024
Public toxic database	Self-supervised learning,	GIN	Tox21, ToxCast, ClinTox	3-layers : AUROC = 71.8	Zang et

	Supervised learning			5-layers: AUROC = 73.7	al.2023
Public toxic database	Self-supervised, Transfer learning	GIN	Tox21, ToxCast, ClinTox	AUROC=78.1, 66.5, 73.7 on test	Hu et al. 2020
15 Environmental End Point Dataset	Contrastive learning, Supervised learning	GAT	Self-collected from literature	$R^2 > 0.9$	Wang et al.2023
Public toxic database	Semi-supervised learning	GCN	Tox21	AUROC=0.757 on test	Chen et al.2021
Chemical Estrogenicity	Supervised learning	1D CNN	Self-collected from multi database	Total accuracy on internal/external test = 0.88, 0.925	Wang et al. 2021
Zebrafish Larvae Morphometric Analysis	Supervised learning	Mask R-CNN	Self-collected	Mean average precision > 0.93	Dong et al.2023
Acute Toxicity of Organic Compounds	Supervised learning	1D CNN	ChemIDplus	$R^2 = 0.7$ on external set	Daghighi et al.2024
5-HT reuptake inhibitor	Supervised learning	CNN-GRU	NCBI	$R^2_{\text{adjusted}} > 0.9$	Sun et al. 2024
Public toxic database	Supervised learning	CNN	Tox21	Average AUC=0.85	Yuan et al.

					2019
Molecular-specific mutagenic alerts	Supervised learning	1D-CNN	ISSSTY	F1-score=0.78 on test	Chen et al. 2024
Public toxic database	Supervised learning	Smi2Vec-BiGRU	Tox21, ToxCast, ClinTox	AUROC=0.78, 0.97, 0.64 on test	Lin et al. 2020
Public toxic database	Supervised learning	BiGRU	Tox21, ClinTox, ToxB	Average AUROC=0.94, 0.95, 0.91 on test	Peng et al.2019
Three endpoints of Ames mutagenicity, Inhibition of P. falciparum Dd2 and Inhibition of Hepatitis C Virus	Supervised learning	LSTM	Self-collected from multi database	AUROC > 0.9	K. Chakravarti et al. 2019
Ecotoxicology	Supervised learning	RoBERTa	REACH, U.S. EPA ECOTOX, EFSA	Median error factors=2.66, 2.82 on fish and aquatic invertebrates	Gustavsson et al. 2024
Toxicology	Supervised learning	MolBERT	CATMoS Datasets	ACC=0.86-0.87	Norinder et al. 2023
Toxic protein and peptide	Transfer learning	ProteinBERT	UniProt	MCC=0.64 and AUC=0.86 on test	Morozov et al.2023

Public toxic database	Multi-task learning	DNN	Tox21	AUROC=0.853	Li et al.2020
PFAS Toxicity	Transfer learning	DNN	EPA Toxicity Estimation Software Tool (TEST), NIH Collaborative Acute Toxicity Modeling Suite (CATMoS), and National Toxicology Program datasets	R ² =0.6	Feinstein et al. 2021
Acute toxicity	Multi-task learning	DNN + GCNN	ChemIDplus	R ² =0.57	Jain et al. 2021

Fig.1 The key milestones in QSAR and machine learning and deep learning evolution in the field toxicity prediction.

Fig.2 Feature engineering vs feature learning for capturing important similarity relationships. Molecular embeddings created using handcrafted descriptors are often high-dimensional and sparse, making it challenging to capture the similarities between molecules. In contrast, deep representation learning leverages loss functions to automatically learn node embeddings. The molecular representations learned through this process are low-dimensional and dense, effectively capturing the similarities between molecules, which enhances the accuracy of downstream predictors.

1

2

3 Fig.3 Graph data processed by GNN. GNNs use adjacency matrices to define graph structures and transmit information between nodes through message passing.

4 Aggregation functions summarize information from neighbors, while update functions refine node embeddings. These embeddings are used for node-level, edge-level,

5 and graph-level tasks, capturing complex relationships and patterns in graphs

6

7 Fig.4 Schematic diagram of a convolutional neural network (CNN). CNNs excel at processing structured data in Euclidean space. They use convolutional layers to
 8 capture details like edges and textures, and pooling layers to downsample data, retaining essential features and improving efficiency. These features are then used in
 9 fully connected or classification layers for accurate recognition and analysis.

10

11
 12 Fig.5 Learning from SMILES representation by RNN and Transformers. Molecular structures can be converted into SMILES strings, which use ASCII characters to
 13 describe molecules. These strings are input into language models like RNNs and Transformers. The encoders map each element into high-dimensional space,
 14 extracting rich molecular semantics through techniques like multi-head self-attention and residual modules. This information can be used for tasks such as molecular
 15 toxicity prediction.

16

17 Fig. 6 An illustration of advanced machine learning processes. By employing these various training methods, denser and more accurate molecular embeddings can be

18 obtained, which not only effectively mitigate the issue of inaccurate activity cliff predictions but also provide more reliable results in the context of insufficient

19 toxicity datasets.

20

21 Fig. 7 This graphic shows how a deep learning encoder can learn data distribution of a given dataset to generate smooth and continuous latent representation,

22 allowing for capture the similarity of complex structures within the data and inverse design of small molecules with targeted properties.

23